

Intrusion Detection and Automated Monitoring for Protection of Critical Infrastructures

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Abstract

Critical infrastructures have continued to be the object of attacks globally. Critical infrastructures can either be digital or physical infrastructures and the attacks on such infrastructures are generally considered as cyber-attacks and vandalism. In Nigeria, traditional methods such as perimeter fencing, use of security operatives and others have been attempted to protect these devices but with little success rate. This study proposes a tech-driven approach of intrusion monitoring and detection to protect critical infrastructure. It adopts a microcontroller-based system integrated with Passive Infrared (PIR) sensors, GSM module and powered with a solar panel for round-the-clock operation. To implement the developed intrusion detection system, a laboratory-scale power distribution substation model was developed with the intrusion detection system incorporated. The developed system report intrusion via mobile call to preset mobile phone number and also a buzzer alarm was set off to alert the immediate neighborhood of an intruder. Experimental results revealed that at minimum sensitivity, the range of PIR sensor coverage was 6 m, 8 m with medium sensitivity and 16 m with maximum sensitivity. Even though increased PIR sensitivity resulted in improved sensor range there was drawback due to increased latency in GSM communication to stakeholders regarding detected intrusion. The developed system would be useful in preventing intrusion, vandalism and theft of physical infrastructures in Nigeria and Africa.

Keywords: *Intrusion Detection, Automated Monitoring, Critical Infrastructure, PIR Sensor*

1 Introduction

Globally, the trend in the attacks on national and utility infrastructures has continued unabated [1]. These infrastructures are categorized as critical because of the catastrophic damage it produces on the society and the economy if destroyed. Critical infrastructures are broadly classified into digital and physical infrastructures [2]. Digital infrastructures consist of information installations and devices used for the transmission of packets of data while physical infrastructures are facilities categorized as restricted areas. Intrusion into digital infrastructures is classified as cyber-attacks and the intrusion into physical infrastructures is described as perimeter intrusion. More appropriately, intrusion into physical infrastructures is regarded as vandalism and theft.

Electricity is a vital critical infrastructure that supports vital societal functions [3]. Telecommunication infrastructure is also another important critical infrastructure which comprises both physical and digital components [4]. These infrastructures have continued to suffer from threats and attacks in Nigeria. The use of information and communication technology for the coordination, control and supervision of traditional grids have resulted in digital power grids [5]. This has made modern power systems cyber-physical in nature.

Against this backdrop, there has been a significant increase in the cyber-attacks against electrical infrastructures and digital power grid substation. These attacks are targeted against hardware, software and network topology [5]–[6]. Several successful cyber-attacks on power grids have been recorded

since 2015 in developed economies including Ukraine, United States of America (USA), Turkey and Switzerland [6]–[7].

In developing economies, vandalism and attack on physical infrastructures continues unabated. The authors [1] reported on persistent cases of vandalism and theft of power and communication system infrastructures in countries across South America, Africa and Asia. Several reasons that motivate intrusion into physical infrastructures includes financial, social, economic, political factors among others [8]. In another study, cable theft and vandalism was reported in Pakistan and the associated effect on both the utility and the consumers. The study reported that copper cable theft and vandalism in transformer, substation and underground wiring are serious issues facing the utility in Pakistan. The impact and cost of these vandalism and attacks on the infrastructure includes infrastructure deficit, loss of lives and property, huge cost incurred in repair among others [9].

The Nigerian government have enacted the “Designation and Protection of Critical National Information Infrastructure Order, 2024” to ensure the protection of critical infrastructure such as power grids, telecommunication networks in Nigeria. The enactment of the Order has brought to the fore the perennial problem of the attack on critical infrastructure in Nigeria. The act of vandalism of electricity infrastructure have affected all sectors of the power supply system [8] in their study gave a comprehensive report on the various attacks and vandalism on the Nigerian transmission lines including location and towers affected from 2014 - 2023. These attacks have continued unabated with 86 towers vandalized in 2024

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while 42 attacks were carried out on the Nigerian transmission line, thereby affecting 178 towers that were vandalized in 2025 [10]. However, the cases of vandalism of distribution substation being localized are too numerous to account for on the national level. This underscores the high rate of vandalism and attack on these critical infrastructures.

1.1. Mitigation of Intrusion

The work of [11] described the five (5) strategies recommended by Crime Prevention through Environmental Design (CPTED) to prevent crime which includes surveillance,

access management, territoriality, activity support, and maintenance. The study posited that surveillance is the most important strategy to be employed to safeguard a facility. Furthermore, the two (2) types of surveillance strategy are natural and artificial surveillance. Electronic monitoring is considered the most sophisticated approach in artificial surveillance. This has been the most widely used approach for intrusion detection in critical infrastructure. The classification of approaches for intrusion mitigation developed is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Classification of intrusion detection and mitigation techniques

a) Vandalism mitigation: Traditional Approach

A typical distribution substation and telecommunication base station in Nigeria is provided with perimeter fencing as the only protection from intrusion. For a power distribution substation when vandalized, a common approach is to use traditional approaches described in Fig. 1 which is as shown in Fig. 2. The outlined approaches do not provide adequate and sufficient protection for all the substation equipment. Therefore, the adoption of suitable technology to protect utilities infrastructures is an urgent requirement in physical infrastructure design [12]

Fig. 2 Traditional power distribution substations protection against vandalism and theft

b) Vandalism mitigation: Technological Approach

Apart from the traditional approaches, technologically-driven approaches are now being used to secure critical infrastructures. These might include the use of image-based technology such as the installation of CCTV, and more

commonly the installation of Internet of Things-based devices is being employed to detect intrusion in real-time and report such to operators. Other intrusion detection systems (IDS) include geo-fencing and geospatial approaches using satellite communication. These intrusion detection devices used to combat intrusion threats are referred as IDS devices designed to detect and identify and report intrusion attack on an infrastructure. Hence, an IDS detects an intruder intending to gain an unauthorized access into a system or infrastructure [13]. IDS are hardware or software systems designed to monitor and protect digital and physical infrastructures against attacks [2].

Table 1 shows the contribution of many researchers to the development of intrusion detection systems for physical infrastructures using technological approach. The authors in [14] used a single sensor for intrusion detection. The use of single PIR sensor may not provide total coverage of the critical infrastructure. Also, IoT monitoring without local alert may not create the prompt response to prevent intruders. The study in [15] used two PIR sensors for intrusion detection but the developed IDS system was dependent on the BLYNK platform for turning ON/OFF. Hence, when the BLYNK platform was turned OFF, the device automatically turned OFF. In [16], a two-layer security function was used for intrusion detection. IoT monitoring and local alert was integrated into the system to detect intrusion but the loss of RFID card and/or forgetting the numerical code could make the facility inaccessible. Authors in [17] used microwave sensor used in the study suffered from false alarm because it does not operate continuously and hence there is high possibility of missing an intrusion. The authors in [18] used sophisticated camera for facial recognition to detect intrusion. This might compromise intrusion detection because theft and/or vandalism are not only perpetuated by unknown persons and the sophisticated camera makes the developed system highly expensive. In [19], a three-layer sensor was used

for intrusion detection. The system designed used multiple notification stages through alarm trigger, GSM messaging and local notification on LCD. The limitation of this study is that GSM notification and local LCD display may not create the instant awareness required for quick response to the intrusion. Authors in [20] used a single-layer sensor for intrusion detection. The system was capable of detection of motion in dark by reducing the infrared filtering from the CMOS sensor. The system was designed to give alert to user through operation of lighting signal or buzzer sound. It is a low power intruder detection system, but has a complex processing system. The study in [21] used multimodal sensors so as to be able to differentiate between actual intrusion and false alarm using the behavioral analysis of the data collected from the sensors. The integrational of multiple sensors would make the system highly expensive. Also, initial large data was required to train the

machine learning model to identify the different pattern from the sensors. From Table 1, IoT-based approach has been used in mitigation of intrusion focused with focus on homes and buildings infrastructures [14]–[18]. Some of them were already implemented [15]–[16], [18]–[19], while others remained in the theoretical concept level [14],[17]. From the review, it could be found that 70% of the cases, addressed home or building protection with only two cases addressing power and telecommunication system infrastructure as shown in [19 - 20]. As a result of dearth of literature on design of intrusion protection and detection system for power and communication system infrastructure to curb incessant vandalism and theft. The unique contribution of this study is to design and implement a prototype intrusion detection system suitable for installation in a power and telecommunication substation.

Table 1. Review of intrusion detection in physical infrastructures

Paper	Attack type		Mitigation Approach	Implementation	Application
	Physical	Type			
[14]	✓	IoT-based	Arduino, Node MCU, Ultrasonic sensor, Blynk application	No	Home
[15]	✓	IoT-based	Passive Infrared sensor, Infrared (IR) sensor, ESPresso Lite V2.0 microcontroller, FAVORIOT database platform, Blynk platform	Yes	Home
[16]	✓	IoT-based	RFID sensor, Blynk App, buzzer, pin code keypad	Yes	Home
[17]	✓	IoT-based	Microwave Motion Sensor	No	Building
[18]	✓	Image-based	infrared barrier sensors, Attiny85 microcontroller, Raspberry Pi Pico, wireless barrier, sophisticated camera, network video recorder, alarm system	Yes	Public Building
[19]	✓	IoT-based	Vibration sensor, PIR sensor, Ultrasonic sensor, Current sensor, GSM module SIM800L, Atmega 328 microcontroller	Yes	Underground power and telecommunication installation
[20]	✓	IoT-based	PIR sensor, Arduino GSM shield 2, GSM module	No	Transformer substation
[21]	✓	IoT-based and ML	Acoustic sensor, infrared sensor, seismic sensor	No	Oil-pipeline

2. Methodology

2.1 PIR Sensor Design

The operation of PIR sensor is governed by pyro electric effect in which electric charge is generated due to temperature change as illustrated by equations 1 and 2 [22].

$$\Delta P = p * \Delta T \tag{1}$$

where ΔP is Change in spontaneous polarisation, p is pyro electric coefficient of material, ΔT is temperature change. The electric current produced due to temperature change is governed by equation 2

$$I = p * A * \frac{d(\Delta T)}{dt} \tag{2}$$

In equation 2, I is the current generated as a result of temperature change in the PIR sensor, A is the cross sectional are of sensing element and $\frac{d(\Delta T)}{dt}$ is the rate of change of temperature with time.

2.1 Laboratory-scale model

A laboratory-scale model-based design and implementation of intrusion monitoring and detection system is proposed in this study. It is a setup that depicts a typical power system substation equipment such as transformer, feeder pillar and so on with three PIR sensors strategically position at different angles. The PIR sensors are placed at a height of 13 cm (being the average height if many components on the laboratory-scale model). The system architecture and flowchart of the intrusion monitoring and detection system is shown in Fig. 3 and 4 respectively while Fig. 5 is electronic circuit of the developed intrusion detection

system. The design comprises four (4) units which are motion detection, processing, actuating, and power section.

Fig 3: Architecture of the proposed intrusion detection system

Fig 4: Flowchart of the developed intrusion detection system

Fig 5: Electronic circuit of the developed intrusion detection system

The developed system uses three passive infrared (PIR) sensors (1, 2 and 3) placed at strategic locations within the substation model to detect when an unauthorized entry is made into the substation premises. The motion signals coming from the PIR sensors are connected to digital input of Arduino prototyping

board which in turn connects to GSM module as shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 5. The PIR sensor logic changes to 1 when motion is detected and 0 when there is no motion. If the PIR sensor mode is in 0, this means motion is not detected and so the system initializes and waits for reception of input signals. If the PIR sensor mode changes to 1, this means motion is detected. The SIM 900 GSM shield is triggered to initiate a call through the service provider base station to the stakeholder's mobile phone. In order to ensure adequate and round the clock power supply for the intrusion detection system, a solar-powered option is adopted. This comprises of 18 V solar panel, 20 A charge controller, 12 V battery, used to power the system by means of buck converter.

Fig. 3 illustrates the architecture of the system. It comprises of the sensor layer of PIR sensors 1, 2 and 3 meant for intrusion detection. The detected intrusion signal is transmitted through the network layer comprising of telecommunication devices such as GSM module and cloud services. The last layer is the data management layer where operators (stakeholders) are able to receive feedback of the intrusion detected by the system and take action. Fig. 4 is the flowchart describing the operation of the developed intruder detection system. When the device is switched on, initializes and begins to scan in order to obtain information from any of the PIR sensors. If any signal is detected, digit "1" is assigned and signal is sent to the Arduino microcontroller prototyping board. If no intrusion is detected, the systems returns to initialization level. The detected signal is received by GSM module from the microcontroller and transmitted to designated mobile phone numbers of relevant stakeholders. The activation of the PIR sensors during intrusion detection and signal transmission by GSM module is shown in the code snippet in Fig. 6.

```

if ((digitalRead(PIR_SENSOR1) == HIGH) or (digitalRead(PIR_SENSOR2) == HIGH)
or (digitalRead(PIR_SENSOR3) == HIGH)) // reading PIR output sensor
{
digitalWrite(BUZZER, HIGH); // setting buzzer to high
Serial.println("INTRUDER DETECTED");
Serial.println( );
SIM900.println("ATD + +2348033517745;"); //+2348033517745 SUPO
delay(100);
SIM900.println();
delay(20000);
// AT command to hang up
SIM900.println("ATH"); // hang up
delay(1000);
}
    
```

Fig. 6 Snippet of code illustrating PIR sensors activation

3 Results and Discussion

3.1. Testing and Results

The developed power distribution substation model incorporated with intrusion detection devices is shown in Figure 7. Fig. 7a and b are setups that depict a typical power system substation equipment such as transformer, feeder pillar and so on with three PIR sensors strategically position at different angles. The PIR sensors are placed at a height of 13 cm from the platform due to the height of the model used for the study. For a real power distribution substation, the PIR sensor is still effective for the pole height of 9 – 11 meters which is still within the maximum coverage distance of 12 meters for PIR sensors. Hence, the placement of PIR sensors at a distance of 3 – 7 meters on the electric pole is recommended in practical application.

To test the developed intrusion detection system, a person is made to walk around the laboratory-scale power distribution system in the range of PIR sensors at different distances. Feedback is received on the serial monitor of Arduino Software displayed on a personal computer (PC) and calls received on GSM mobile phone as shown in Fig. 8. When no one is within

the range of the PIR sensors, the intrusion detection system is considered to be in the idle mode. At this time, the serial monitor on the PC in Fig. 8a displays the message “scanning” and at this time in the program section a “0” or “LOW” signal is sent by the microcontroller through its digital output pin to the GSM module as indicated in Table 2. The moment a living object comes into any of the PIR sensor’s range, the idle or scanning mode becomes active, the message “INTRUDER DETECTED” appears on the serial monitor as shown in Fig. 8a. Immediately, a “1” or “HIGH” signal is sent to the digital output pin of the microcontroller to the GSM module as indicated in Tables 2 to 5. The HIGH signal triggers the GSM module to automatically start calling the stakeholder’s mobile phone as shown in Fig. 8b and a buzzer sound is also triggered thus alerting the relevant stakeholders.

Fig. 7: a) Laboratory-scale power system substation with intrusion detection devices System in Idle Mode without an Intruder, b) System in Active Mode when an Intruder is detected at a few distance

Fig. 8 a) Snapshot of the PC serial monitor showing the device in the idle (scanning) mode and active mode when intrusion was detected, b) Call received on stakeholder’s mobile phone due to detected intrusion

Table 2. PIR sensors in the idle and active modes during testing

S/N	PIR sensor 1	PIR sensor 2	PIR sensor 3
1	1	0	0
2	1	0	0
3	0	1	0
4	0	0	1

0 = idle mode, 1= active mode

3.2. PIR sensor Sensitivity Test

PIR sensor sensitivity was investigated with respect to range and latency in GSM communication by adjusting the sensitivity pot of the PIR sensor. The test was carried out outdoor with laboratory-scale model hosting PIR sensor raised to 1.5 m. Maximum sensitivity was achieved by rotating the pot clockwise while minimum sensitivity was when the pot was adjusted anti-clockwise. The response of the PIR sensor to human movement in terms of range and latency of GSM communication were recorded. When sensitivity was minimum, obtained result is shown in Table 3, Table 4 is result of average sensitivity while Table 5 is result of maximum sensitivity.

Table 3. System performance with minimum PIR sensitivity

S/N	Distance(m)	Motion Detected	GSM module communication	GSM response (seconds)
1	2	YES	YES	2
2	4	YES	YES	1
3	6	YES	YES	1
4	8	NO	NO	0
5	10	NO	NO	0
6	12	NO	NO	0
7	14	NO	NO	0
8	16	NO	NO	0
Average GSM response				1

Table 4. System performance with medium (average) PIR sensitivity

S/N	Distance (m)	Motion Detected	GSM Module communication	GSM response (s)
1	2	YES	YES	3
2	4	YES	YES	8
3	6	YES	YES	2
4	8	YES	YES	5
5	10	NO	NO	0
6	12	NO	NO	0
7	14	NO	NO	0
8	16	NO	NO	0
Average GSM response				4

3.3. Discussion of Result

PIR sensor 1 depicted by binary number 1 (active mode) in Table 2 does not only show the presence of an intruder, it also

provides information about the likely direction from where the intrusion is coming from. For instance, if PIR sensor 1 is positioned at the northern corner of the laboratory-scale substation and by default is able to receive intrusion signals covering an angle of about 90° to 180° typically 140° [26 - 27].

Table 5. System performance with maximum PIR sensitivity

S/N	Distance (m)	Motion Detected	GSM Module communication	GSM response (s)
1	2	YES	YES	2
2	4	YES	YES	6
3	6	YES	YES	1
4	8	YES	YES	10
5	10	YES	YES	9
6	12	YES	YES	6
7	14	YES	YES	8
8	16	YES	YES	6
			Average GSM response	6

It therefore implies that the intrusion is likely to be coming from a seemingly opposite direction to the PIR sensor 1 different from the position of the sensor which could be east, west or south. The same condition goes for PIR sensors 2 and 3. One would have expected that to effectively cover the four directions of the substation, four PIR sensors should have been installed. This might not be necessary since the coverage angle of 140° inherent in the three PIR sensors positioned at three corners such that the coverage overlaps each other are believed to provide a 360 degrees coverage of the entire substation. From Table 2, it could be seen that even though the 140° angle allows for overlapping of the PIR sensors implying that more than one could sense an intruder at the same time triggering multiple alerts which could consume more power thus over-draining the DC power source. From Table 2, the device is developed such only one PIR sensor can be activated at the same time minimizing power usage.

Implementation of the laboratory-scale intrusion detection system is a proof-of concept which has the potential of scale. Real-time notification of intrusion would allow speedy intervention in managing intrusion incidences and this is in line with the work of [19, 23 - 25]. This proposed IoT-based approach for power substation protection would be an improvement over the traditional methods in terms of surveillance which is carried out by building perimeter fencing, use of security guards and the likes and is believed go a long way in detection of intrusion and vandalism thereby protecting critical infrastructure and saving millions of naira for the nation and bringing about reliability in the power and telecommunication sectors

From the results in Table 3, 4 and 5, it could be observed that at minimum sensitivity, the range of PIR sensor coverage was 6 m, 8 m with medium sensitivity and 16 m with maximum sensitivity. This implies that coverage area improved with

increased PIR sensitivity. It could also be observed that sensitivity variation also affected the average response time of the GSM communication as shown in Tables 3 to 5. For instance, at minimum sensitivity, average delay (latency) was 1 second, 4 seconds at medium sensitivity and increased to 6 seconds at maximum sensitivity. This implies that though the sensitivity increase resulted in higher sensor range there was a drawback in terms of increased latency of GSM communication. This could be due to false positives, increased noise or re-trigger delay of the PIR sensor [26]. The obtained information would be useful to operators of the PIR sensor to find trade-off between sensor coverage and latency in order to achieve timely reporting of detected intrusion to relevant stakeholders.

4 Conclusion

In this work, intrusion of power and telecommunication system is reviewed in terms of vandalism and cyber-attacks of cyber-physical critical infrastructures. Traditional mitigation approaches were found to be inadequate as well as some technological approaches to curb vandalism. An intrusion detection method for power system distribution substation was developed at a lab-scale as a means of safeguarding the various expensive equipment contained in the substation against vandalism and theft. The proposed system is an automated way of securing expensive power substation equipment and reducing the overhead cost incurred in hiring security personnel who could have been saddled with such security responsibilities. The strategic placement of the three (3) PIR sensors was able to ensure 360 degrees coverage area (120° for each PIR sensor) for the vicinity surrounding the substation. Tests carried out revealed that high PIR sensitivity resulted in increased sensor range but with drawback in term of latency in GSM communication of detected intrusion to relevant stakeholders. Future work will include the incorporation of electronic camera for real-time image capturing and implementation in a power distribution substation.

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